

Automotive Industrial Robot - Selection Criteria for Body Assembly Application

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In automotive manufacturing processes especially at Body Shop, industrial robots are widely used to increase productivity while maintaining desired quality standard and design specification in production line. The application are mainly on welding (spot / arc welding), sealant / adhesive application and material handling. Therefore, the selection of the robot types and brand are crucial in order to get best fit to the application at minimum cost.

Depending on area of application to the automotive body structure, generally, there are 2 types of industrial robots - shelf and floor mounted types. The practical way in robot selection method is by determining the robot specification that meeting process specification and requirement, then, cost evaluation is done by using [Total Cost of Ownership \(TCO\) method](#). The following table shows the comparison of robot specifications, initial and operational cost for different robot's makers which gives general ideas on what to be taken into account during robot selection processes.

Brand	ABB	KUKA	Yaskawa
Picture			
Model	IRB 6700 – 235	KR 210 R2700	MS 210
Payload (Max)	235 kg	210 kg	210 kg
Type	Floor mounted	Floor mounted	Floor mounted
Controller	IRC 5	KR C2 Edition 2005	DX 200
Power Supply	7.7 kVA	7.3 kVA	5.0 kVA
Repeatability	± 0.06 mm	± 0.06 mm	± 0.2 mm
Payload diagram, max COG range (Z-direction)	500mm	600mm	600mm
Axis max speed, °/sec	126.7 (Avg)	108.0 (Avg)	140.3 (Avg)
MTBF (Manufacturer claim)	40,000 hours	40,000 hours	36,000 hours
Robot, Controller & Accessories	RM 124,367	RM 139,689	(Total 1 set)
Dress Pack	RM 4,295 (3 rd party - Leoni)	RM 4,295 (3 rd party - Leoni)	↓
Total, RM / unit	RM 128,662	RM 143,984	RM 155,000
Power consumption, RM/unit/day (1 shift)	RM 6.06	RM 5.95	RM 5.72
Spare part (ABB as reference), %	-	16.6% lower than ABB (Avg)	19.9% lower than ABB (Avg)
Maintenance (Actual), RM / Unit / Year	RM 3,200	-	RM 725
Downtime Cost (Actual), RM / Unit / Year	RM 8,780 (IRB 6640)	-	RM 1,718.75 (ES 200N)

The robot's specifications as stated on the table are suitable for spot welding and material handling applications. First thing to consider is process requirement on position's accuracy. Process position's accuracy (tolerance) has to be matched with robot's repeatability. Then, other specifications such as maximum robot's payload and 'reach work space' to be considered during robot's selection process.

There are some robot's specifications that are usually neglected but quite important especially when it comes into productivity and cost effective point of view. For example, for better productivity, faster robot axis speed is required to complete the process. The following tables shows the comparison of maximum robot axis speed for 3 different robot makers.

Brand	Yaskawa	ABB	KUKA
Picture			
Max Axis Speed, °/sec			
Axis 1	120	100	86
Axis 2	97	90	84
Axis 3	115	90	84
Axis 4	145	170	100
Axis 5	145	120	110
Axis 6	220	190	184
Average	140.3	126.7	108.0

For cost effective point of view, maximum center of gravity (COG) range in robot payload diagram also quite important. The following table shows the comparison of robot payload diagram for 3 different robot makers.

Farther the effective range of allowable maximum payload in robot payload diagram, better the tool's design flexibility and cheaper the tool's material cost. For example, if the designed tool's weight exceed allowable effective range in robot payload diagram, there are 2 options available for designer, either to select higher robot payload spec or to use lightweight material for tool's fabrication. Both options may increase the robot initial or purchase cost.

Estimating the operational cost of a robot is quite difficult but possible and usually neglected during robot selection processes. Other than robot [mean time between failure \(MTBF\)](#) value and spare part cost, robot power consumption during operation also can be estimated. The following tables shows the estimated robot power consumption comparison for 3 different robot makers.

Robot Power Consumption	Max Rating/ Capacity, kVA	Rated Capacity, kW		
		Playback (Robot Moving)	Servo On (Robot Standby)	Servo Off (Power for Control)
Yaskawa	5.0	1.97	1.09	0.28
ABB	7.7	2.7	0.71	0.16
KUKA	7.3	2.5	0.7	0.22

*Power consumption data taken from robot's specification for each brand

Robot	Working Day	Working hours	Idle Hours		Movement type			Shift	Working	Idle	Total Cost, RM/robot/day	Total Cost, RM/robot/month
			Day	Night	Playback	Standby (Servo On)	Standby (Servo Off)		Cost, RM/robot/day	Cost, RM/robot/day		
ABB	22	8	4	12	60%	40%	0%	1	RM5.41	RM0.65	RM6.06	RM133.21
Yaskawa	22	8	4	12	60%	40%	0%	1	RM4.59	RM1.13	RM5.72	RM125.78
KUKA	22	8	4	12	60%	40%	0%	1	RM5.06	RM0.89	RM5.95	RM130.81

*Utilities cost (electricity) is calculated based on 1 shift (day) operation

*Movement type details:

- Playback – Robot move to spot point location / position
- Standby (Servo On) – Robot's position on hold, welding gun perform spot welding operation or at home position
- Standby (Servo Off) – Robot idle, no activities (after working hours)

In conclusion, it is easier to select robot that suit to the process requirement. But, when considering productivity and cost effectiveness, a lot of elements need to be considered during robot selection processes. It is recommended to evaluate [robot total cost of ownership \(TCO\)](#) before finalizing robot selection to get clear picture of overall cost that need to be spent in robotic production line.